

Assessing Macrobenthic Assemblages as Indicators of Organic Pollution In Ankodia Pond, Vadodara District, Gujarat, India

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14686354>

Abstract

This study investigates the macrobenthic assemblages in Ankodia Pond, focusing on species diversity and abundance as indicators of environmental health. Using the Shannon-Wiener diversity index, we found low diversity and evenness suggesting dominance by a few pollution-tolerant families, particularly Chironomidae and Syrphidae. The presence of these bioindicator species, along with Cyprididae, points to significant organic pollution in the pond. Our findings emphasize the importance of monitoring macrobenthic communities to assess water quality and guide effective management strategies for ecosystem restoration.

Keywords: Macrobenthic assemblages, Species diversity, Pollution-tolerant families, Organic pollution, Bioindicator species, Ecosystem restoration

Introduction

Over the past century, researchers have sought a universal indicator to assess wetland quality and detect impacts on biological resources due to the increasing stress on ecosystems (Varandas & Cortes, 2010). In recent decades, macrobenthos has emerged as a particularly important indicator of wetland ecosystem health. These organisms are highly responsive to environmental conditions in wetlands due to their direct contact with

sediment and their role in transferring energy and materials through the ecosystem (Yang et al., 2019). Their essential function in energy and material flow within the food chain makes macrobenthos a crucial component of wetland biocenosis (Yang et al., 2016).

Ankodia Pond is located in Ankodia village, approximately 9 kilometers from the city of Vadodara. Covering an area of 0.94 km², the pond is situated at coordinates 22.3406° N, 73.1149° E.

It is bordered by the village on two sides, with the main village road passing nearby. Due to its proximity to residential colonies, sewage water is discharged into the pond, leading to pollution. Villagers also graze their cattle along its banks. Small-scale fish farming is practiced in the pond, and the local governing body has initiated construction around the banks to enhance its aesthetic appeal.

Methodology

Figure 1. Sample collection using quadrat

Sieving and Organism Separation: A plastic sieve with a 1 mm x 1 mm mesh size was used to separate organisms larger than 1 mm from the collected samples. Water was gently sprinkled over the sieve to remove excess

The study was conducted over a three-month period from January to March 2022.

Sampling Method: The Quadrat Sampling Method was used to collect macrobenthic samples from shallow areas of the pond. A quadrat with dimensions of 50 cm x 50 cm and a depth of 4 cm was utilized for sample collection. Samples were taken from five different locations along the pond banks, all collected during morning hours.

Figure 2. Quadrat samples locations

sediment, using low pressure to avoid damaging the organisms.

Preservation of Samples: Organisms were preserved immediately after collection. Hard-bodied organisms were stored in 70% alcohol, while soft-

bodied organisms were preserved in 10% formaldehyde.

Data analysis

The following methos was used to analyze the data and calculate the species diversity and evenness indices.

- 1) Shannon-Wiener Diversity Index (Shannon and Wiener ,1949)

$H = -\sum p_i \ln p_i$, Where, H= Shannon-Wiener Diversity Index, p_i = the relative abundance of each group of organisms.

- 2) Pielou’s Evenness Index (Pielou, 1966)

$J' = H / H_{max}$, Where, J' = Pielou evenness index, H= The observed value of Shannon index, $H_{max} = \ln S$, S= Total number of species

Results

During the study, a total of 1,335 macrobenthic individuals representing

seven different families were identified. In the first quadrat, 910 organisms from three families—Cyprididae, Chironomidae, and Corixidae—were recorded, along with one unidentified family. The second quadrat contained 65 organisms from two families, Cyprididae and Chironomidae, along with one unidentified family. Similarly, in the third quadrat, 132 organisms from Cyprididae, Chironomidae, and Hydrophilidae, plus one unidentified family, were observed. In the fourth quadrat, 223 individuals from three families—Cyprididae, Chironomidae, and Hydrophilidae—were identified. Finally, in the fifth quadrat, 19 individuals from Cyprididae, Corixidae, Syrphidae, Bithynidae, Libellulidae, and one unidentified family were recorded. Family-wise number of organisms is provided in Table 1 and quadrat-wise numbers in

Table 1. Family-wise number of organisms encountered during the study	
Family	Organisms encountered
Bithynidae	02
Corixidae	03
Chironomidae	182
Cyprididae	1143
Hydrophilidae	02
Libellulidae	01
Syrphidae	02
Unidentified	14
Total (identified; excluding unidentified)	1335

The study results revealed that the species diversity index was 0.5059 and evenness index was 0.2433.

Table 2. Quadrat-wise details of number of organisms encountered for various families

Family	Q-1	Q-2	Q-3	Q-4	Q-5
Bithynidae	0	0	0	0	2
Corixidae	1	0	0	0	2
Chironomidae	4	56	120	2	0
Cyprididae	904	4	5	220	10
Hydrophilidae	0	0	1	1	0
Libellulidae	0	0	0	0	1
Syrphidae	0	0	0	0	2
Unidentified	1	5	6	0	2
Total	910	65	132	223	19

Figure 3. Proportion of organisms of macrobenthic families in Ankodia Pond

Discussion

The Shannon-Wiener diversity index of 0.5059 and an evenness value of 0.2433 for the macrobenthic assemblages in Ankodia Pond indicate low species diversity and an uneven distribution. This suggests that a few

species dominate the community, signaling an ecological imbalance (Heip, 1974). The Cyprididae family, which constitutes a significant portion of the assemblage, is commonly found in freshwater environments (Martens et al., 2008). Their capacity to

disperse through drought-resistant eggs enables them to thrive in stressful conditions, and their high numbers in the pond likely reflect their resilience and adaptability. The Chironomidae family, known to inhabit polluted waters, has larvae that tolerate organic pollution and feed on algae, diatoms, and bacteria (Pinder, 1986; Saether, 1979). Their abundance in Ankodia Pond points to significant organic contamination.

The presence of Syrphidae, whose larvae develop in decaying organic matter, further supports evidence of pollution. As filter feeders associated with polluted habitats, they indicate organic accumulation and poor water quality (Miranda & Rotheray, 2018). Other families, such as Hydrophilidae, are also indicative of stagnant or low-flow conditions, as their larvae are poor swimmers and thrive in ponds with minimal water movement (Minoshima et al., 2018). The dominance of these families suggests that the pond environment may favor species that can tolerate or thrive in polluted, stagnant waters.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the dominance of pollution-tolerant species such as

Chironomidae and Syrphidae, along with low diversity and uneven distribution, indicates that Ankodia Pond is affected by organic pollution. The abundance of these species reflects environmental stress and underscores the importance of using macrobenthic communities as indicators of water quality. Effective monitoring and management are essential to address these issues and help restore the pond's ecological health..

Acknowledgments

We would like to express our gratitude to Prof. Geeta Padate and Dr. Chandni Valodkar for their invaluable guidance throughout this study. We also extend our thanks to Prof. Kauresh D. Vachhrajani, Dr. Khushali Pandya, Mr. Nikunj Vasava, Mr. Shantanu Karandikar, and Mr. Keyur Bhatti for their support.

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